

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CARBON NANOTUBE/CARBON FIBER MULTI-SCALE REINFORCEMENT

C. Wang¹, X. D. He^{1*}, L. Y. Tong², Y. B. Li¹, Q. Y. Peng¹, L. Mei¹, R. G. Wang¹

¹ Centre for Composite Materials and Structures, Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin 150080, China, ² School of Aerospace, Mechanical and Mechatronic Engineering, The University of Sydney, NSW 2006, Sydney, Australia

* Corresponding author(xdhe@hit.edu.cn)

Keywords: *carbon nanotubes; carbon fiber; dendrimers; multi-scale reinforcement; pullout model*

1. Introduction

The interfacial shear strength between a CF and epoxy resin matrix plays an important role in determining the mechanical properties of composite. The fiber-matrix interface in a composite can be improved via various surface treatments, such as oxidation and coating etc; however, the improvement may be limited. Recently, some researchers successfully grew CNTs onto CF or fabrics by Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD) [1-3] and showed that the insertion of CNTs improves the interfacial strength and subsequently the delamination toughness [4-5]. However, despite of the enhancement, the catalyzer and the high temperature involved in the CVD process can also degrade the strength of carbon fiber and the interfacial shear strength [6]. Recently, our research group focused on using the chemical grafting methods to assemble the CNTs onto CFs [7-8]. The SEM photograph of CNTs/CF multi-scale reinforcement is shown in Figure 1. The mechanical testing results shows that there is an excellent interfacial shear strength between the CNTs/CF and matrix [9].

In order to estimate the interfacial enhancement of CNTs/CF reinforced composites, it is important to determine the interfacial shear strength between CNT and matrix. Wanger et al. [10] performed the fragmentation experiment, and the results show that there is strong stress transfer ability and the interfacial shear stress of CNT/polyurethane system can reach 500MPa . Cooper et al. [11] first detached single CNT from matrix and showed that the interfacial shear strength of CNT/epoxy system ranges from 35 to 376MPa . Although the evidence of experiments indicated that there is a strong interfacial bonding between CNT and matrix, it is still a challenging issue to manipulate carbon nanotubes in experiments. The MM and MD

simulations have been widely used in studying the interfacial mechanical properties of nanocomposites [12-13]. Liao et al. [14] studied the interfacial shear stress of CNT/polystyrene system, in which the interfacial shear stress was assumed to be constant along the axial direction of CNT. Gou et al. [15] carried out the pullout simulation of CNT from epoxy matrix, and the interfacial shear strength between CNT and epoxy matrix was estimated as 75MPa . Zheng et al. [16] studied the effect of chemisorption on the interfacial properties between CNT and polymer by simulating the pullout of CNT, and the results show that by chemically functionalizing CNTs the interfacial shear strength can be improved. The above statement has indicated that the simulation of MM and MD is an effective method to investigate the mechanical properties of nano-reinforcement reinforced composites.

In this study, firstly, the MM and MD were employed to simulate the pullout of CNT from epoxy resin matrix and the interfacial bonding characteristics of CNT and epoxy resin matrix were investigated. Then a simple micromechanical model for evaluating the interfacial shear strength of CNTs/CF reinforced composites was established by combining the numerical results from MM and MD.

2. Computational model

2.1 Molecular Model of CNT

In this study, a double-walled CNT was constructed by using Materials Studio with the length of 59.03\AA and diameter of 13.56\AA , respectively, as shown in Fig. 2. The unsaturated boundary effect is removed by adding the hydrogen atoms at the two ends of the CNT.

2.2 Molecular Model of Cured Epoxy Resin Matrix

The epoxy resin matrix comprises of DGEBA resin and triethylenetetramine curing agent, the molecular structures of which are shown in Fig. 3. For the epoxy resin matrix, the degree of

polymerization was set at 1. The single molecule models of the agent and resin were constructed first, and then the energy minimization was performed to optimize the molecule structures. One hydrogen atom of amine groups on agent molecule can react with the epoxide group of one end of epoxy resin molecule first, and then the other hydrogen atoms of amine groups on the agent molecule can further react with epoxide groups, the epoxide group of another end of epoxy resin molecular can react with other agent molecule, as the reaction lasted, the agent molecules and epoxy resin molecules can generate cross-links [15]. Although the above cross-linked mechanism can be used to generate a cured epoxy system, it is very complex to be applied in larger molecular model system. In this study, we employed a method of representative cross-linked unit to simulate the cured epoxy system, and it has been testified to be a valid method to obtain the requested epoxy system [17]. According to this method, the cured epoxy system is composed of the simple representative cross-linked unit, which is composed of four epoxy resin molecular and one curing agent molecular as shown in Fig. 4.

2.2.3 Molecular Model of CNT/Epoxy Resin System

Packing the representative cross-linked unit molecular of epoxy resin and CNT into a supercell in the range of $50.00\text{\AA} \times 50.00\text{\AA} \times 65.00\text{\AA}$, and the initial configuration was made to ensure that the CNT can be surrounded by the cured epoxy resin with a density of 1.00g/cm^3 . Then the molecular system of composite was equilibrated for 20ps while keeping the CNT rigid. A further equilibrium of 30ps was performed with non-rigid CNT. Lastly a sufficient energy optimization was carried out to achieve the strongest interfacial bonding between CNT and matrix as shown in Fig. 4 [15].

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Interfacial Bonding of CNT and Epoxy Resin Matrix

The bonding strength of CNT and epoxy matrix is related to the interfacial interaction energy. The interfacial interaction energy can be calculated by the difference between the potential energy of composite molecular system and the potential energy of the matrix molecular and the embedded CNT as follows [16]:

$$\Delta E = E_{total} - (E_{matrix} - E_{CNT}) \quad (1)$$

where ΔE is the potential energy of the composite molecular system, E_{matrix} is the potential energy of matrix, and E_{CNT} is the potential energy of CNT. The interfacial interaction energy, ΔE , is twice the

interfacial bonding energy γ scaled by the contact area A [18]

$$\gamma = \frac{\Delta E}{2A} \quad (2)$$

In order to determine the interfacial shear strength of CNT and matrix, the pullout simulation of CNT from matrix was performed. The interfacial shear strength can be evaluated by the pullout energy of CNT from matrix, which is defined as the energy difference between the fully embedded CNT and entire pullout configuration [15-16]. The pullout energy can be divided into three terms which include the energy change of CNT, matrix, and their interaction energy after and before CNT pullout simulation as follows [15-16]

$$\begin{aligned} E_{pullout} &= E_{total2} - E_{total1} \\ &= (\Delta E_2 - \Delta E_1) + (E_{matrix2} - E_{matrix1}) \\ &\quad + (E_{CNT2} - E_{CNT1}) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where E_{total2} and E_{total1} are the energy of CNT/epoxy resin system after and before CNT pullout from matrix, respectively. E_{matrix} and E_{CNT} are the energy of matrix and CNT. ΔE is the interaction energy between CNT and matrix. There exists the following relation between the pullout energy and the interfacial shear stress τ_i [15-16]

$$E_{pullout} = \int_0^l 2\pi r(l - \delta)\tau_i d\delta \quad (4)$$

$$\tau_i = \frac{E_{pullout}}{\pi r l^2} \quad (5)$$

where r and l are the radius and length of CNT, respectively. δ is the pullout displacement of CNT. The three different pullout phases are shown in Fig. 5. During the pullout of CNT from matrix, the changes of interfacial interaction energy and bonding energy with pullout displacement are shown in Fig. 6 and 7, respectively. It can be seen that the absolute value of the interaction energy gradually decreases due to the reduction of the contact area between CNT and matrix, and the interfacial bonding energy varies in a range from 0.15 to 0.19 kcal/mol \AA^2 , and this indicates that there is a steady interface adhesion during pullout of CNT. From the relation of the pullout energy and displacement as shown in Fig. 8, it is noted that the pullout energy almost linearly increases with the pullout displacement. This is because the pullout load needs to overcome the interfacial bonding energy, the deformation energy of CNT and matrix. Finally we can obtain that the interfacial shear strength between

CNT and matrix is about 60.52 MPa from the pullout simulation, which is comparable to that in another epoxy system [15].

3.2 Interfacial Shear Strength of CNTs/CF Reinforced Composite

Several test methods have been developed to evaluate the interfacial shear strength of fiber reinforced composite, for example microdroplet test [19], pullout test [20] and fragmentation test [21]. The microdroplet test is employed because the preparation for specimen is relatively easy and it can be used in small diameter fiber, such as CF etc. Furthermore, in microdroplet test, the interfacial shear stress is assumed to be constant along the fiber axis which simplifies the analysis and calculation. The interfacial shear strength of common CF reinforced composite from microdroplet test can be expressed as follows [22]

$$\tau = \frac{F}{\pi D_f L} \quad (6)$$

where τ is the interface shear strength between a CF and its matrix, F is the maximum pull load, D_f is the diameter of CF, and L is the length of CF embedded into the epoxy droplet. In order to evaluate the interfacial shear strength of CNTs/CF reinforced composite, it is assumed that the interfacial shear stress between CNTs/CF and matrix is uniform along the CF axis and increases with the applied load until the maximum is reached when the interfacial shear stress reaches the its strength as described in the micro-droplet [22]. So equation (6) can be employed to estimate the interfacial shear strength between CNTs/CF and matrix as shown in Fig. 9a.

As shown in Fig. 9b, for the pullout of the fiber from matrix at angle ϕ , the matrix exerts a normal stress at exit point on the fiber to allow axial force of fiber to change its direction, because of the normal stress effect, the snubbing effect will contribute to the increase of axial force, so the maximum pullout force of inclined fiber can be expressed as [23]

$$F_{CNT} = F_* \exp(f\phi) \quad (7)$$

where f is the snubbing friction coefficient, and F_* is the maximum pullout force of CNT along axial direction of CNT. Here we used equation (7) to estimate the maximum pullout of CNT. Because CNTs are highly flexible, the snubbing friction coefficient of CNT can be neglected as an approximation, i.e. $f = 0$ [24]. So we can obtain a simplified expression as follows

$$F_{CNT} = F_* = \pi d_{CNT} l_{CNT} \tau_{CNT} \quad (8)$$

where d_{CNT} and l_{CNT} are the actual diameter and length of CNT, τ_{CNT} is the interfacial shear strength between CNT and matrix obtained from the molecular simulation. In this study, equation (8) means that in the pullout of inclined CNT from matrix, there is no contribution of snubbing effect to the maximum pullout load, and the CNT can be pulled out as a flexible string, in which only the axial interfacial friction contributes to the maximum load. So the maximum pullout load F_1 of CNTs/CF reinforced composite can be expressed as

$$F_1 = F_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n F_*^i \quad (9)$$

where n is the number of CNTs embedded into micro-droplet on CF. Combining equations (6), (8) and (9), the interfacial shear strength τ_1 of CNTs/CF reinforced composite can be expressed as

$$\tau_1 = \frac{F_1}{\pi D_f L} = \frac{\pi D_f L \tau_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \pi d_{CNT}^i l_{CNT}^i \tau_{CNT}^i}{\pi D_f L} \quad (10)$$

where τ_0 is the interfacial shear strength before grafting CNTs between the CF and matrix obtained from micro-droplet testing. From Fig. 1, it can be seen that the CNTs are uniformly grafted on CF, and it is reasonable to use average diameter \bar{d}_{CNT} and length \bar{l}_{CNT} of CNTs and the average CNT distribution density $\bar{\rho}_{CNT}$ defined as the number of CNTs per square micrometer. Hence equation (10) can be simplified as

$$\tau_1 = \tau_0 + \pi \bar{\rho}_{CNT} \bar{d}_{CNT} \bar{l}_{CNT} \tau_{CNT} \quad (11)$$

In order to validate the above model and investigate the enhancement effect of CNTs, the microdroplet testing was conducted, the details on preparation of different CF specimens can be found in Mei et al. [8]. The cured epoxy matrix was composed of the DGEBA and triethylenetetramine with a ratio of 10:1. The testing results are listed in Table 1. The interfacial shear strength of CF/CNTs reinforced composite was measured as 106.25 MPa which represents an increase of 73.41 % compared to that of the treated CF reinforced composite. In order to compare with the experimental results, the average diameter, length and distribution density of CNTs were determined statistically from a number of SEM photographs, and they are 30 nm, 600 nm and 17, respectively. By using equation (28), it is

predicted that there is an increase of 94.52 % duo to the enhancement effect of CNTs, which is comparable to the microdroplet testing result. It is worth noting that in this study it is assumed that all the CNTs can be pullout from matrix, and the snubbing effect and angle effect in the interfacial enhancement are negligible. In the future work, expected is development of an enhanced theoretical model for forecasting the interfacial shear strength of CNTs/CF reinforced composite.

4. Conclusions

In this study, there is a strongly interfacial bonding between the CNT and epoxy resin matrix and a numerical value of interfacial shear strength of 60.52 MPa was obtained by implementing the MM and MD. The theoretical study combining with the numerical results shows that the interfacial shear strength of CNTs/CF reinforced composite can be improved by 94.52 % duo to the additional CNTs on CF surface, and which is agreeable with the experimental result.

Acknowledgment

This work was supported by the Major Research Plan of the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No. 90816005), and the State Scholarship Fund from China Scholarship Council (CSC) for overseas study.

References

- [1] Q.H. Zhang, J.W. Liu, R. Sager, L. Dai, J. Baur. *Composites Science and Technology*, 69, pp 594-601, 2009.
- [2] J.G. Zhao, L. Liu, Q.G. Guo, J.L. Shi, G.T. Zhai, J.R. Song, Z.J. Liu. *Carbon*, 46, pp 380-383, 2008.
- [3] Z.G. Zhao, L.J. Ci, H.M. Cheng, J.B. Bai. *Carbon*, 43, pp 651-673, 2005.
- [4] K.L. Kepple, G.P. Sanborn, P.A. Lacasse, K.M. Gruenberg, W.J. Ready. *Carbon*, 46, pp 2026-2033, 2008.
- [5] L.Y. Tong, X.N. Sun, P. Tan. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 42, pp 5-23, 2008.
- [6] E. T. Thostenson, W. Z. Li, D. Z. Wang, Z. F. Ren, T. W. Chou. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 91, pp 6034-6037, 2002.
- [7] X.D. He, F.H. Zhang, R.G. Wang, W.B. Liu. *Carbon*, 45, pp 2559-2563, 2007.
- [8]. L. Mei, X.D. He, Y.B. Li, R.G. Wang, C. Wang, Q.G. Peng. *Materials Letters*, 64, pp 2505-2508, 2010.
- [9] F.H. Zhang, R.G. Wang, X.D. He, C. Wang, L.N. Ren. *Journal of Materials Science*, 44, pp 3574-3577, 2009.
- [10] H. D. Wagner, O. Lourie, Y. Feldman, R. Tenne. *Applied Physics Letters*, 72, pp 188-190, 1998.
- [11] C.A. Cooper, S.R. Cohen, A.H. Barber, H. D. Wagner. *Applied Physics Letters*, 81, pp 3873-3875, 2002.
- [12] M. R. Nyden, S. I. Stoliarov. *Polymer*, 49, pp 635-641, 2008.
- [13] C. Lv, Q.Z. Xue, D. Xia, M. Ma, J. Xie, H.J. Chen. *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 114, pp 6588-6594, 2010.

- [14] K. Liao, S. Li. *Applied Physics Letters*, 79, PP 4225-4227, 2001.
- [15] J.H. Gou, B. Minaie, B. Wang, Z.Y. Liang, C. Zhang. *Computational Materials Science*, 31, pp 225-236, 2004.
- [16] Q.B. Zheng, Q.Z. Xue, K.Y. Yan, X.L. Gao, Q. Li, L.Z. Hao. *Polymer*, 49, pp 800-808, 2008.
- [17] S.Y. Yu, S.H. Yang, M.H. Cho. *Polymer*, 50, pp 945-952, 2009.
- [18] V. Lordi, N. J. Yao *Mater. Res.*, 15, pp 2770-2779, 2000.
- [19] S.K. Kang, D.B. Lee, N.S. Choi. *Composites Science and Technology*, 69, pp 245-251, 2009.
- [20].J.P. Favre, M.C. Merienne *Int. J. Adhes. Adhes.*, 1, pp 311-316, 1981.
- [21] H.D. Wagner, H.E. Gallis, E. Wiesel *J. Mater. Sci.*, 28, pp 2238-2244, 1993.
- [22] B. Miller, P. Muri, L. Rebenfeld. *Composites Science and Technology.*, 28, 17-32, 1987.
- [23] S.Y. Fu, B.L. Zhou, C.W. Lung. *Composites Science and Technology*, 47, 245-250, 1993.
- [24] S.Y. Fu, Z.K. Chen, S. Hong, C.C. Han. *Carbon*, 47, pp 3192-3200, 2009.

Fig.1. SEM photograph of a single CCMR.

Fig. 2. Molecular model of CNT.

Fig. 3. Molecular structures of epoxy resin and curing agent.

Fig. 4 The molecular model of CNT reinforced composite. (a) Cross-linked epoxy unit (b) Molecular system of CNT/epoxy resin matrix.

Fig. 5 The snapshots of the pullout of CNT from molecular simulation.

Fig. 6 The relation plot of interfacial interaction energy-pullout displacement.

Fig. 7 The relation plot of interfacial bonding energy-pullout displacement.

Fig. 8. The relation plot of pullout energy-pullout displacement of CNT during pullout simulation.

Fig. 9. Sketch of microdroplet test for the interfacial shear strength of CNTs/CF reinforced composites.

Table 1 Interfacial shear strengths of different CF reinforced composites in micro-droplet test

	Interface shear strength (MPa)
Treated CF	61.27 ± 15.03
CF/CNTs	106.25 ± 23.76